

A Comparative Study of Preservative Potential of Ginger and Bitter Kola for Tomato Preservation

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Abstract

Tomatoes are preserved to extend their shelf life and prevent wastage due to their high-water content and perishable nature. Using plant extracts as preservatives offers several benefits, such as keeping tomatoes free from chemicals and their associated long-term health risks, while enhancing tomato antioxidant and antimicrobial properties, but maintaining tomatoes nutrients, and having minimal effects on tomatoes overall quality. This study examined the potential of ginger and bitter kola extracts as natural preservatives for tomatoes. Ripe tomatoes were soaked in hot water extracts of ginger, bitter kola, and a combination of both, referred to as GE, BKE, and GBE, respectively. The tomatoes were monitored daily for signs of decay and weight loss while glucose, fructose, potassium, total solids, citric acid, and ascorbic acid levels were measured on days 6, 18, and 29 for the 30-day period of the experiment. Between days 0 and 6, all samples showed weight loss, colour changes, and loss of firmness. From days 6 to 29, glucose remained relatively stable in GE (7.5–7.57 mg/100g) and BKE (7.5–8.21 mg/100g), but it decreased in GBE (9.4–6.54 mg/100g). Ascorbic acid levels remained fairly stable in BKE (28.52–27.04 mg/100g), but decreased significantly in GE (32.45–15.24 mg/100g) and GBE (43.76–17.05 mg/100g). Fructose loss was most pronounced in GE (3.4–2.43 mg/100g), followed by GBE (3.95–3.63 mg/100g) and BKE (3.35–2.9 mg/100g). The results indicated that bitter kola showed potential for preserving tomato quality though there were challenges related to nutrient loss and microbial resistance.

Keywords: *Tomato, Bitter kola, ginger, preservation, waste prevention, natural preservatives.*

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Introduction

Tomatoes (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill) are vegetables that are widely consumed around the world and can be eaten raw, cooked, or processed into various forms such as paste, puree, stew, sauce, or juice (Banu et al., 2020; Kator et al., 2018; Amadi et al., 2019). Despite their significant economic and nutritional value, tomatoes are highly susceptible to deterioration which occurs through various pathways, including chemical reactions, pest and microbial attacks; with microbial activity being the most significant contributor due to microbial rapid multiplication and widespread dispersion, as well as, high moisture content of tomatoes, which is an ideal medium for microbial growth (Hammond et al., 2015; Hamad, 2012; Rawat, 2015; Singh and Anderson, 2004). Tomato spoilage problem is particularly exacerbated by inadequate storage infrastructure in developing countries,

which contributes to large-scale post-harvest losses (Goka et al., 2021). The consequences of tomato spoilage impact all members of the tomato supply chain as wasting tomato translates to wasting the water, labour, and fertilizer used to produce it. Furthermore, additional pressure is placed on available land as more farmland is needed to feed the same population, and more land must be designated for disposing of the wasted tomatoes. Farmers and marketers face reduced profit margins, as spoiled tomatoes often cannot be sold, preventing them from recovering production costs. Tomato spoilage also contributes to shortage in tomato supply and consequent price increase of the available tomatoes, leading to a higher cost of living for consumers. In an effort to reduce expenses, consumers may cut back on the quantity or quality of the purchased tomatoes, which can result in various nutritional health issues; including malnutrition and food poisoning. Governments are not exempt from the repercussions of tomato spoilage, as they must allocate more funds for importation of tomatoes, the disposal of spoilt tomatoes, healthcare services to manage spoilage-related illnesses, and subsidies for farmers and tomatoes marketers who may struggle financially due to low incomes. Tomato scarcity, along with the rise in living costs, can also lead to increased unrest and insecurity within the population.

As a result, there is a growing demand for safe, effective, and affordable preservation methods to extend the shelf life of tomatoes. A significant portion of research in this area has focused on utilizing plant extracts as natural preservatives to reduce spoilage and maintain the quality of tomatoes. Various techniques, including salting, canning, drying, freeze-drying, pasteurization, irradiation, as well as, usage of preservatives or additives (monosodium glutamate (MSG), potassium sorbate, propionic acid, and sodium benzoate, butylated hydroxyanisole (BHA), butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT)); are employed for preservation of tomatoes to enhance their durability and quality (Gokoglu, 2019; Silva et al., 2016; Kumari et al., 2019). However, some of the preservative techniques have their associated negative health effects; for example, MSG is associated with headaches and nausea, butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT) and butylated hydroxyanisole (BHA) may increase hypersensitivity and cancer risks, while sodium benzoate had been shown to possess carcinogenic and neurotoxic properties (Kumari et al., 2019; Silva & Lidon, 2016). Consequently, there have been growing demand for safer, more natural alternatives (plant-based preservatives) to synthetic preservatives. Recent studies have shown promising results for plant-based preservatives, for example, filtered guava juice had been found to inhibit the growth of *E. coli* O157:H17 and *Salmonella* (Ibrahim et al., 2011). Extracts from *xonocostle* pears had shown similar effects on *E. coli* (Hayek & Ibrahim, 2012). Corbo et al. (2008) reported that grapefruit seed and lemon extracts could increase the microbial stability of fish hamburgers, specifically inhibiting *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Photobacterium phosphoreum*, and *Shewanella putrefaciens*. In studies on seafood preservation, extracts of oregano, thyme, and clove were found to enhance the efficacy of ice storage in controlling aerobic, mesophilic, and psychrophilic bacteria (Bensid et al., 2014). Pomegranate peel extract also reduced bacterial growth and volatile nitrogen levels in Pacific white shrimp (Basiri et al., 2015). Several other plant extracts show significant antimicrobial activity. For instance, thyme exhibits strong activity against *S. aureus*, while garlic and onion inhibit *Saccharomyces* and *E. coli*. Clove has been shown to inhibit growth of *E. coli* and *S. aureus* (Gupta et al., 2012), and nine species of *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* (Azzouz and Bullerman, 1982). Citrus fruits have been shown to inhibit *S. typhi* and *S. aureus* (Chaisawadi et al., 2005). Antioxidant and antimicrobial activity had also been observed in foods treated with essential oils from various plants. For example, essential oils from lemon, citrus, and bergamot showed antimicrobial properties against *S. aureus* in sardines (Djenane, 2015), while cinnamon oil inhibited *Listeria monocytogenes* in minced fish (Abdollahzadeh et al., 2014). Additionally, combinations of thyme essential oil and nisin have been found effective against *Listeria monocytogenes* in minced fish (Abdollahzadeh et al., 2014). Other essential oils like coriander and lemongrass have proven effective against *C. albicans*, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Rhizopus digosporus* (Chao et al., 2000). The increasing recognition of the antimicrobial,

antioxidant, and preservative potential of plant extracts has led to their growing use as natural preservatives in food systems, offering an alternative to synthetic chemicals. Sometimes, a naturally occurring mineral compound like alum can be used as a preservative. For example, Amadi et al. (2019) investigated the antimycotic potential of alum, showing that a 1% (w/v) aqueous solution of alum effectively inhibited the growth of spoilage fungi such as *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium* spp., and *Fusarium* spp., commonly found on decaying tomato fruits. This suggests that alum could be a potential natural preservative for tomatoes, preventing fungal decay.

Banu et al. (2020) examined the use of gels made from aqueous extracts of *Kappaphycus alvarezii* and *Sargassum tenerrimum* seaweed species for preserving tomatoes. The treated tomatoes exhibited lower weight loss, better texture, and higher ascorbic acid levels, juice and moisture contents, and total suspended solids compared to untreated controls. Additionally, the seaweed extracts showed antibacterial activity against various pathogens including *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Proteus mirabilis*, suggesting their potential to both preserve and enhance the quality of tomatoes. In another study, Ejechi et al. (1999) tested the effectiveness of phenolic acid and essential oil extracts of peppercorn in reducing fungal growth in blended tomato samples. The combined extracts significantly reduced fungal growth and carbohydrate loss. However, when used individually, the essential oil and phenolic acid extracts led to an increase in fungal counts and a reduction in carbohydrate content, highlighting the importance of combining these extracts for effective preservation. Olaley et al. (2014) explored the preservation of tomatoes using aqueous extracts from *Carica papaya*, *Xylopiya aethiopica*, *Piper nigrum*, and *Tetrapleura tetraptera*. They found that the aqueous extract of *Carica papaya* at a concentration of 0.25 mg/mL provided the most significant increase in shelf life, indicating the potential of these medicinal plants as natural preservatives. Tzortzakis et al. (2019) studied the use of coatings made from *Aloe vera* and sage essential oils on tomatoes. The coated tomatoes exhibited improved firmness and higher antioxidant activity but showed lower levels of beta-carotene, lycopene, and acidity compared to untreated controls, suggesting a trade-off between preservation and the retention of certain nutritional qualities.

Ginger (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe) is widely recognized for its rich chemical composition, including bioactive compounds like gingerol and shogaol, which provide antioxidant and antimicrobial properties. These properties make ginger a promising natural preservative in food preservation. Several studies have investigated the antimicrobial potential of ginger in preserving different food products by inhibiting microbial growth, reducing oxidation, and maintaining the overall quality of the food. For example, Nguetack et al. (2004) extracted essential oils from fresh ginger rhizomes and emulsified them. The emulsion showed moderate activity against fungi such as *Fusarium moniliforme*, *Aspergillus flavus*, and *Aspergillus fumigatus*, with higher concentrations (800–1000 ppm) exhibiting stronger antifungal effects. Similarly, El Ghorab et al. (2010) demonstrated that both fresh and dried ginger essential oils exhibited over 80% of 2, 2-diphenyl-1—picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical scavenging activity, indicating strong antioxidant properties. Sacchetti et al. (2005) noted that ginger essential oil prepared by steam distillation demonstrated over 50% DPPH free radical scavenging activity and over 60% inhibition of beta-carotene bleaching, along with antimicrobial effects against various fungi such as *Candida albicans*, *Rhodotorula glutinis*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Schizosaccharomyces pombe*, and *Yarrowia lipolytica*. However, its antimicrobial efficacy was noted to be moderate when compared to other essential oils. Ajayi and Bankole (2020) added aqueous ginger extracts to tiger nut milk and found that the treated milk scored higher in appearance, aroma, consistency, and general acceptability than the untreated control. The ginger-treated samples also had a more consistent pH and showed smaller changes in total titratable acidity, which suggests that ginger can help in maintaining the quality of perishable beverages. Similarly, Ajayi et al. (2016) blended zobo juice with 0.5% and 1% (w/v) ginger powder and pasteurized it. The ginger-treated samples showed smaller pH rises compared to untreated controls for both refrigerated and

unrefrigerated samples. Additionally, vitamin C content increased in ginger-treated samples, and bacterial counts were lower than those in untreated samples. While fungal counts were initially higher, they decreased significantly after 2, 4, 6, and 8 weeks in unrefrigerated ginger samples. The appearance, acceptability, and aroma of ginger-treated samples were also better preserved.

Arekemase and Babashola (2019) explored the combined effect of ginger and clove extracts as preservatives for soy milk. They found that the ginger-clove mixture significantly reduced bacterial and fungal growth compared to the untreated controls. The preservation effect was observed for more than 15 days for 1% and 3% ginger-clove extracts and up to 20 days for the 5% extract. In addition, the ginger-clove samples exhibited higher protein and fat content and smaller drops in pH and titratable acidity, demonstrating the additive benefit of combining these two plant extracts for food preservation. In another study by Belewu et al. (2005), ginger extract was added to West African soft cheese. The ginger-treated cheese exhibited a reduction in both fungal and bacterial growth compared to untreated samples. The antimicrobial activity was attributed to the presence of bioactive compounds such as gingerol and shogaol, suggesting that ginger could be an effective natural preservative in dairy products. Ipinmoroti (2018) investigated the use of ginger juice for preserving *Clarias gariepinus* (catfish). Fish treated with different concentrations of ginger juice showed lower microbial populations (both fungal and bacterial) compared to saline-treated samples. Additionally, the ginger-treated fish had reduced levels of aflatoxins and peroxides, indicating that ginger antimicrobial and antioxidant properties were effective in reducing spoilage and maintaining the quality of the fish. The results also indicated a concentration-dependent effect, with the 75% ginger juice sample showing the best preservation. Nwokocha (2012) tested ginger extract as a preservative for zobo juice and found that it helped maintain vitamin C levels, pH values, and total titratable acidity, while also inhibiting bacterial and fungal proliferation compared to untreated juice. Similarly, Olaniran et al. (2020) observed that ginger-treated juice had comparable sensory qualities to untreated juice and sodium benzoate-treated juice. Ginger-treated juice showed lower microbial counts, and the variations in pH, total soluble solids, and specific gravity were also smaller compared to the untreated samples, suggesting that ginger could be a viable alternative to synthetic preservatives. The use of ginger as a natural preservative in various food products has been shown to effectively reduce microbial growth, prevent oxidation, and maintain the quality of the food. Its antimicrobial and antioxidant properties, attributed to compounds such as gingerol and shogaol, make it a promising alternative to synthetic preservatives. The versatility of ginger in preserving dairy products, juices, fish, and beverages demonstrates its potential to be incorporated into a wide range of food preservation applications. Future studies could further optimize its use and explore the potential for combining ginger with other natural preservatives to enhance its effectiveness.

The study by Olaniran et al. (2013) demonstrated the effectiveness of ginger powder in preserving the antioxidant properties of tomato paste. Specifically, it was found that the tomato paste treated with ginger powder showed higher DPPH scavenging activity and phenolic content compared to the untreated control. Additionally, the rate of decline in DPPH scavenging activity, phenolic content, and lycopene concentration was slower in the ginger-treated paste, suggesting that ginger powder can help maintain the nutritional and antioxidant quality of tomato paste for a longer period. This finding supports the potential of ginger as a natural preservative to prevent oxidative degradation and preserve key beneficial compounds in processed food products like tomato paste.

Regarding bitter kola (*Garcinia kola*), its potential as a natural food preservative has been widely investigated, and several studies have demonstrated its antimicrobial and antioxidant properties, which make it a promising candidate for use in food preservation. Bitter kola contains several bioactive compounds, including flavonoids, tannins, saponins, cardiac glycosides, steroids, and reducing sugars, which contribute to its antimicrobial and antioxidant effects. Research by

Adegboye (2008) showed that the methanol extract of *Garcinia kola* exhibited antibacterial activity against *Bacillus anthracis*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Bacillus cereus*. Similarly, extracts from the butanol and diethyl ether fractions of *Garcinia kola* demonstrated antibacterial activity against *Bacillus anthracis* and *E. coli* (Akinpelu et al., 2008). These findings suggest that bitter kola can potentially inhibit the growth of food spoilage bacteria and pathogens, thereby prolonging the shelf life of food products. In addition to its antibacterial properties, *Garcinia kola* has shown antifungal effects. Methanol and aqueous extracts of the plant have been found to inhibit the growth of *Streptococcus mutans*, a cariogenic bacterium (Afolabi et al., 2008), and crude ethanol extracts demonstrated antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Streptococcus viridans*, *E. coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Klebsiella pneumonia* (Akerele et al., 2008). Further studies by Akinnibosun et al. (2013) and Mbotto et al. (2009) explored the combination of *Garcinia kola* aqueous extract with honey, which was found to be effective against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and *Salmonella* species, along with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Candida albicans*. This combination demonstrated enhanced antimicrobial effects compared to individual treatments, highlighting the synergistic potential of *Garcinia kola* when used in conjunction with other natural substances. The antioxidant properties of bitter kola are also notable. A study by Dah-nouvlessounon et al. (2015) found that the ethyl acetate extract of *Garcinia kola* seeds exhibited the highest DPPH scavenging activity, indicating strong antioxidant properties. This antioxidant activity helps in preventing oxidative damage to food, thus extending its freshness and quality. Moreover, bitter kola extracts have shown effectiveness in reducing microbial contamination in wastewater. Okoh et al. (2011) tested crude n-hexane extracts of bitter kola seeds against *Vibrio* strains and found that the extracts achieved over 90% microbial kill rates after two hours of exposure, further supporting its potential as a natural preservative. Overall, bitter kola has proven to be a potent antimicrobial and antioxidant agent, making it an effective and safe alternative for use in food preservation. Its ability to inhibit the growth of spoilage organisms and protect against oxidative damage can significantly improve the shelf life and safety of various food products.

Although several studies have been carried out on tomato preservation; there is a dearth of literatures on using ginger and bitter kola for tomato preservation. Hence, this study focused on using the two natural preservatives to extend tomato shelf life. Application of natural preservatives for tomato preservation in developing countries will help the farmers to overcome challenges of inconsistent power supply for tomato refrigeration, the high cost of preservation equipment, and a lack of technical expertise in equipment usage and maintenance; which is often the case when using advanced preservation techniques like irradiation, freezing, and pasteurization. The usage of natural preservatives for extending tomato shelf life has the potential to be a reliable, safe, and affordable preservation technique.

Materials and Methods

This methodology provided a detailed and systematic approach to evaluating the effectiveness of ginger, bitter kola, and their combination as natural preservatives for tomatoes. Through these analyses, we aimed to assess their impact on various quality parameters, including appearance, texture, and nutritional content.

Materials

The experimental materials used in this study were obtained from a local Nigerian market. The materials include ripe tomatoes (*Lycopersicon esculentum*), fresh ginger rhizomes (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe), and bitter kola seeds (*Garcinia kola*). Apparatus used included blender, containers for tomatoes preservation, freezer, mesh net and weighing balance.

Methods

The tomatoes, fresh ginger rhizomes, and bitter kola seeds were thoroughly washed under running water to remove any dirt or dust. For the preparation of extracts, 100 g of ginger rhizomes and bitter kola seeds were each sliced into 1-2 mm thick pieces. These slices were then blended separately with about 200 mL of distilled water in an electronic blender for 2 minutes to obtain a homogenous pulp. This step was essential for improving the extraction process and ensuring an even distribution of the plant materials in the final extract. The extracts used in the study were ginger extract (GE), bitter kola seed extract (BKE), and combination of ginger and bitter kola extract (GBE). Additionally, tomatoes without any preservatives (UC) served as the control group. For the preparation of GE, 300 mL of distilled water was added to 200 mL of ginger rhizome pulp in a clean aluminum pot. This mixture was boiled for 30 minutes to prepare a 20% (w/v) mixture. The resulting mixture was transferred to a sterile round-bottomed flask (1000 mL), shaken vigorously to enhance the extraction, and filtered using a clean filter cloth. The filtered extract was stored in an opaque container, clearly labeled as GE. Two batches of GE, labeled GE-1 and GE-2, were prepared. The same method was repeated for bitter kola seeds to obtain BKE, with two batches labeled BKE-1 and BKE-2. For GBE, a mixture of 50 g dried bitter kola seeds and 50 g dried ginger rhizomes was prepared using the same hot water extraction method described for GE and BKE. Two batches of GBE, labeled GBE-1 and GBE-2, were prepared while two control batches of tomatoes, UC-1 and UC-2, were also included. The ripe tomato fruits were placed in porous bags, with each bag containing 20-30 fruits. These bags were fully immersed in the containers containing the respective extracts or the control medium. The containers were kept in a cool, dry place at room temperature for the duration of the study. The tomatoes were observed daily for the parameters, including appearance (red color intensity), firmness, defects, and changes in tomato weight. The tomatoes were observed daily for the appearance (red color intensity), firmness, defects, and changes in tomato weight. Additionally, physicochemical tests, including total solids, glucose and fructose contents, citric acid, vitamin C (Ascorbic Acid), potassium ion concentration; were carried out at 6, 18, and 29 days of storage.

Results

The results obtained from the observations made regarding the tomatoes appearance (red color intensity), firmness and defects, and tomato weight, are presented in Tables 1, Figure 1, and Figure 2. Regarding the physicochemical analysis, which includes total solids content and nutrient content, the results are presented in Tables 2 and Table 3.

Table 1. Appearance (Red Color Intensity)

	DAY 5	DAY 10	DAY 15	DAY 20	DAY 25	DAY 29
GE1	Red	Red	Red	Red	Reddish yellow	Reddish yellow
GE2	Red	Red	Red	Reddish yellow	Reddish yellow	Reddish yellow
BKE1	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
BKE2	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
GBE1	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
GBE2	Red	Red	Reddish yellow	Reddish yellow	Red	Red
UC1	Red	Reddish yellow	Reddish yellow	Ended	Ended	Ended
UC2	Red	Reddish yellow	Reddish yellow	Reddish yellow	Ended	Ended

Figure 1. Firmness and Defects
Note: F = firm, B = bloated, D = defective

Figure 2. Average Tomato Weight (grams)

Table 2. Total Solids Content

		INITIAL WEIGHT (g)	FINAL WEIGHT (g)	PERCENT TOTAL SOLIDS
DAY 6	UC	44.8	1.04	2.32143
	GE	18.5	1.05	5.67568
	BKE	35.9	1.11	3.09192
	GBE	12.5	1.34	10.72000
DAY 12	UC	8.5	1.15	13.52941
DAY 18	GE	4.5	0.58	12.88889
	BKE	13.5	1.13	8.37037
	GBE	15	0.81	5.40000
DAY 24	UC	9.5	0.54	5.68421
DAY 29	GE	8.5	0.67	7.88235
	BKE	4	0.43	10.75000
	GBE	8.5	0.56	6.58824

Table 3. Nutrient Content

		GLUCOSE (mg/100g Sample)	FRUCTOSE (mg/100g Sample)	CITRIC ACID (mg/100g Sample)	ASCORBIC ACID (mg/100g Sample)	POTASSSIUM CONCENTRATION (mg/L)
DAY 6	UC	10.02	4.4	8.64	46.06	19.1
	GE	7.5	3.4	5.6	32.45	15.4
	BKE	7.5	3.35	8	28.52	24.3
	GBE	9.4	3.95	5.44	43.76	19.2
DAY 18	UC	8.12	3.63	8	36.72	19.5
	GE	8.28	3.06	4.8	23.93	10.2
	BKE	6.63	3.86	5.44	20.00	7.7
	GBE	8.08	2.76	3.2	25.41	7.2
DAY 29	GE	7.57	2.43	2.4	15.24	8.9
	BKE	8.21	2.9	4.8	27.04	10
	GBE	6.54	3.63	4.8	17.05	7.6

Discussion

The quality and consumer acceptability of tomatoes and tomato products are influenced by their total solids, soluble solids, acid content, sugar-to-acid ratio, vitamin C concentration, and potassium concentration. In addition to these physicochemical parameters, organoleptic properties like flavor, consistency, color, and aroma are also significant factors for food processors and consumers. The preservation of tomatoes during storage is crucial not only for maintaining their visual appeal but also for their nutritional and flavor quality. The current study explored the impact of different preservative extracts on these parameters over a period of time.

Tomato Color

A progressive change in color from red to reddish-yellow was observed in all preservative samples and control groups. This discoloration is typical of vegetable crops during storage (Xylia et al., 2021). Such discoloration could indicate a decline in the lycopene concentration, which is

responsible for the vibrant red color in healthy tomatoes. The loss of lycopene has been commonly observed in stored tomatoes, with a higher rate of degradation in untreated tomatoes compared to those treated with conventional preservatives (Sarkar et al., 2015). In this study, discoloration was observed most quickly in the untreated control tomatoes, suggesting that the preservative extracts used in the treatment were more effective in preventing or delaying the degradation of lycopene and maintaining the vibrant red color.

Regarding Ginger Extract (GE) and Bitter Kola Extract (BKE), the color remained mostly red throughout the observation period, with slight discoloration to reddish-yellow only by the later days of the experiment (days 25-29). For the Ginger and Bitter Kola Extract (GBE), the samples, similarly, retained the red color for an extended period, with a slight transition to reddish-yellow observed towards the later days, especially in the GBE-2 batch. The untreated control (UC) tomatoes began showing discoloration by day 10, with full discoloration to yellow by day 20, indicating quicker degradation compared to the treated samples. This observation suggests that the application of ginger extract, bitter kola extract, and their combination was effective in delaying color degradation compared to the untreated controls. The natural preservatives helped maintain the visual appeal of the tomatoes by slowing down the breakdown of lycopene, thus prolonging the vibrant red appearance of the tomatoes.

Tomato Firmness and Defects

As seen in Figure 1, the firmness of the tomatoes and the occurrence of defects were observed in all samples. The firmness of the tomatoes was maintained for a brief period in both treated and untreated groups. The tomatoes treated with both Ginger Extract (GE) and Bitter Kola Extract (BKE) showed the highest degree of firmness over the course of the experiment. This is indicative of better preservation and slower spoilage in these treated samples compared to the untreated control group. The control group (UC) exhibited significant defects such as bloating and rotting starting from day 18 onwards, which led to their complete degradation by day 25. In contrast, tomatoes treated with GE, BKE, and GBE showed a lower incidence of defects, particularly in the first 20 days, demonstrating the protective effects of these extracts in delaying spoilage.

Average Tomato Weight

From Figure 2, it can be observed that the average weight of tomatoes declined with storage time, but the rate of weight loss was slower in the preservative-treated groups compared to the untreated control. As observed, BKE (Bitter Kola Extract) and GBE (Ginger-Bitter Kola Extract) were more effective in preserving the weight of tomatoes compared to untreated controls (UC). BKE-1 and GBE-1 showed the least weight loss after 24 days, losing only 74.6% and 69.7% of their original weight, respectively, compared to nearly 100% weight loss in the untreated groups. This suggests that the preservatives, especially BKE, helped reduce moisture loss, which is a significant factor contributing to the weight loss of tomatoes. This reduction in weight loss was also reported in previous studies, such as Banu et al. (2020), who showed that seaweed extracts can significantly preserve tomato weight. The loss of tomato weight in all groups, including the preserved ones, is believed to be due to moisture loss through evaporation and the activity of microorganisms that contribute to spoilage. In the untreated tomatoes, larvae-like organisms were observed, indicating microbial degradation, which further accelerated moisture loss and weight reduction.

Total Solids Content

Table 2 shows the total solids content of the tomatoes over the storage period with inconsistency in the percentage of total solids over time. The UC, GE, BKE, and GBE samples all show significant fluctuations in percent total solids across different days. The GBE sample on Day 6 and BKE on Day 29 have unusually high percent total solids values. The percent total solids for UC

shows a large increase on Day 12 and a significant drop on Day 24, which is abnormal. The GE sample shows erratic behavior with a large increase and decrease in percent total solids between different days. A possible cause of the abnormalities observed might be due to contamination from the particles of plant extracts adding to the total solids content of the tomatoes.

Nutrient Content

As seen in Table 3, there were significant changes in the nutrient composition of tomatoes throughout the storage period. The nutrient content, including glucose, fructose, citric acid, ascorbic acid, and potassium concentrations, varied over time and between treatments. Glucose levels remained relatively stable in BKE and GE-treated tomatoes, showing only minor fluctuations. In contrast, GBE and untreated tomatoes experienced a sharp decline in glucose levels, which can likely be attributed to microbial activity that utilizes sugars for growth. Fructose content also decreased over time in all samples, with microbial activity being a major contributor to this reduction. Citric acid, a key contributor to the sour taste of tomatoes, decreased across all groups. The UC group showed the smallest reduction (8.64 – 8.0 mg/100g), whereas BKE experienced the largest decrease (8.0 – 5.44 mg/100g). This reduction is likely due to microbial metabolism of citric acid during ripening, as noted in previous studies (Kator et al., 2018). The ascorbic acid content (Vitamin C) of tomatoes treated with preservatives (GE, BKE, GBE) showed a slower reduction compared to the untreated controls. This suggests that the preservative extracts contributed to the retention of vitamin C. Potassium levels decreased in all tomato samples over the course of the study. Potassium concentration was fairly stable in the treated samples, though slightly lower in GE and GBE by Day 29, possibly reflecting different metabolic responses in treated tomatoes compared to the controls. Potassium plays a vital role in maintaining cellular function and stability in tomatoes. Its reduction could be indicative of the ongoing metabolic processes and the overall decline in the fruit's quality during storage. This supports findings by Ajayi and Oderinde (2013), who reported reduced potassium concentrations in tomato products after long-term storage.

Conclusion

The study demonstrates that the use of natural preservative extracts, particularly Ginger Extract (GE), Bitter Kola Extract (BKE), and their combination (GBE), effectively delayed the degradation of tomatoes and preserved their quality during storage. The findings from this study indicated that ginger and bitter kola extracts have potential as natural preservatives for tomatoes, with bitter kola showing greater effectiveness in preserving tomato quality. While both extracts helped delay decay and maintain certain nutrients, such as glucose and potassium, there were challenges regarding nutrient loss, particularly in ascorbic acid and fructose. Despite these challenges, bitter kola extract (BKE) proved to be a more effective preservative than ginger extract (GE) and their combination (GBE), offering a promising alternative to chemical preservatives for extending the shelf life and maintaining the quality of tomatoes. Conclusively, natural preservative extracts, particularly Ginger Extract, Bitter Kola Extract, and their combination, helped maintain key tomato attributes like colour, firmness, weight, total solids, and nutrient content, compared to untreated control tomatoes. Tomatoes treated with these extracts retained a more vibrant color, slower weight loss, better firmness, and higher levels of essential nutrients like vitamin C, glucose, and potassium. The results suggest that these natural preservatives offer a viable solution for extending the shelf life and improving the quality of tomatoes during storage, making them a promising alternative to conventional preservation methods.

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Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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